

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

dto-bioflow.eu

**EXPLORE MORE
USE CASES**

From Data to Decisions: DTO-BioFlow Use Cases

DUC 5 - Linking Species Traits to
Support Ecosystem-based Marine
Spatial Planning

Funded by
the European Union

From Insight to Impact

The Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs) are at the heart of the DTO-BioFlow initiative, translating complex scientific capabilities into tangible digital solutions for marine biodiversity monitoring and management.

Designed to showcase the power of an **end-to-end digital approach**, these use cases connect cutting-edge biodiversity observations with AI-enhanced models, analytical tools, and the infrastructure of the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO).

Each DUC serves as a living example of how real-world marine challenges can be addressed through integrated digital workflows. They all address a pressing challenge for ocean sustainability and proposes an integrated, evidence-based solution.

DUC 5 focuses on the ecosystem-based spatial planning & MPA management.

Marine habitats provide vital ecosystem services—such as carbon sequestration, habitat buffering, and biodiversity support, but species-level traits underpinning these services remain largely unlinked to spatial planning and MPA design. This use case builds a **species-traits database** to map benthic biodiversity to ecosystem services, enabling more informed and ecosystem-based marine spatial planning.

Challenge

Current planning overlooks specific biological traits that underpin ecosystem services.

Without linking traits (e.g. filter feeding, burrowing) to functional outcomes, planners lack precise tools to evaluate how human activities impact service delivery.

Solution

This DUC creates a public species-traits database, connecting biological traits to ecosystem services via asset-service matrices.

Statistical models then assess how pressures like coastal development or fishing might alter service delivery, informing adaptive and sustainable MPA planning.

Data and monitoring networks used

Species distribution and habitat data, trait and functional data, spacial datas, Human pressure layers.

EMODnet
European Marine
Observation and
Data Network

OBIS
OCEAN BIODIVERSITY
INFORMATION SYSTEM

EMODnet

BIOLOGY

LifeWatch
ERIC

FishBase

MarLIN
Marine Biological Association

Expected Outputs

A species-trait database linked to ecosystem services

Trait-to-service models showing how pressures affect service delivery

Planning Tools to guide adaptive MPA and spatial planning decisions

Digital Twin Capabilities Demonstrated

- **Functional mapping:** Links species traits to ecosystem services across space
- **Pressure response modelling:** Simulates how human activities alter service delivery
- **Knowledge integration:** Combines ecological, functional, and spatial data for planning support

Useful for

- Marine spatial planners
- Conservation managers
- Policy advisor

Learn more on development and read the publications

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Consortium

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